

Research Article

Geopolymerization of Industrial By-Products and Study of Their Stability upon Firing Treatment

***H.M. Khater and Sayieda R. Zedane**

Housing and Building National Research Centre (HBNRC)

87 El-Tahreer St., Dokki, Giza, P.O. Box 1770 Cairo

*Corresponding Author's Email: Hkhat4@yahoo.com

Abstract

There is a growing interest in the development of new cementitious binders which enhance optimal utilization of industrial by-products such as phosphogypsum, fly ash and cement dust. Among all the industrial by-products, fly ash predominates as an alternative building material for building construction activities. Cement kiln dust (CKD) with its high alkali content in the activation of geopolymer specimens to create nonconventional cementitious binders was investigated. Relatively high alkaline content of CKD is predominant factor preventing its recycling in cement manufacture. However, it was observed that depending on the water-soluble alkalis and sulfate compounds, CKD could provide the necessary environment to activate geopolymer materials. Phosphogypsum that is rich in sulfate will enhance geopolymerization process when added in a lower dose. Materials used in this investigation are fly ash (FA), phosphogypsum (PG) and cement kiln dust (CKD) calcined. Phosphogypsum was partially replaced fly ash in the ratio from 0 up to 50%, while the remaining ratio is for cement dust. Alkaline activation by 2 % NaOH along with the added cement dust was studied and the used water to binder ratio is 0.55. Curing was performed under 100 % relative humidity at 60°C. Results showed that 10% PG is the optimum ratio for geopolymer formation and results in best enhancement in mechanical as well as microstructural characteristics. Firing treatment for both 10 and 20% PG mixes possess a lower strength values up to 800°C, while strength exposed to strength gain up to 1200°C.

Keywords: cement dust, phosphogypsum, Fly ash, alkali, firing.

1. Introduction

Alkaline activation is a chemical process whereby silicoaluminate materials with amorphous or vitreous structures are transformed, via interaction with highly alkaline solutions and moderate curing, into products with good cementitious properties, known as a "green" cement [1–3], because through the use of industrial wastes such as geothermal silica, fly ashes and mineralogical slag as source materials, there is the possibility to achieve a significantly lower CO₂ emission per tone in comparison with OPC [1,2,4]. With increasing production volumes, geopolymer and other alkali-activated binders are also becoming cost-competitive with Portland cement, and have found utilization in major infrastructure projects internationally; initially in the former Soviet Union and in China, and now increasingly in Australia and elsewhere internationally as the political and financial incentives for CO₂ emission reductions grow [3]. The main reaction product formed in this process is a three-dimensional alkaline silicoaluminate gel (N-A-S-H gel). A number of zeolites are obtained as secondary reaction products (Palomo et al. 1999, Palomo et al. 2004, Fernández-Jiménez and Palomo 2005, Duxon et al. 2007). Alkaline activation procedures, which are highly versatile, can be used to activate a large number of materials with compositions based on the SiO-AIO-CaO system (such as metakaolin, slag and fly ash).

Moreover, Cement kiln dust (CKD) is generated in cement manufacture and represents fine grained particles of raw materials, partially processed feed and components of final product carried out from the kiln by the exhaust gases. These materials are collected in kiln's air pollution control systems (cyclones, electrostatic precipitators or bag house). The generation of CKD is responsible for a significant financial loss to the cement industry in terms of the value of raw materials, processing, energy usage, dust collection and disposal. Cement manufacturing plants generate approximately 30 million tons of CKD worldwide per year [Dyer et al. (1999)]. CKD can be recycled in

cement manufacturing (if its content in alkali or chlorine does not affect the cement quality) or it can be use in alternative applications such as agriculture, sewage and water treatment, civil engineering (filler or soil and sludge stabilization) and others (Peethamparan et al., 2008, Maslehuddin et al., 2008, Konsta-Gdoutos and Shah, 2003). If CKD's content in alkali and sulfate is high it can be used as an activator for pozzolanic or latent hydraulic materials. Both chemical and physical characteristics of the CKD and aluminosilicate source (fly ash, slag, metakaolinite etc.) play a decisive role in controlling the mechanisms of activation, the nature and amount of formed products and consequently the strength development (Konsta-Gdoutos and Shah, 2003, Wang et al., 2004, Buchwald and Schultz, 2005).

Large quantities of industrial by-products are produced every year by chemical and agricultural process industries. These materials such as fly ash and phosphogypsum have dual problems of disposal and health hazards. With the more and more wastes being generated, the utilization of fly ash and phosphogypsum is important to save the environment from quick degradation. Phosphogypsum (Beretka et al., 1996) and flue gas desulfurization gypsum (Marroccoli et al., 2008) can entirely replace natural gypsum. In particular, fluidized bed combustion (FBC) waste (Arjunan et al., 1999; Bernardo et al., 2003; Marroccoli et al., 2009), a mixture of coal ash and spent limestone sorbent generated during the combined process of coal combustion - "in situ" gas desulfurization within a fluidized bed reactor, is worthy of consideration due to its ability to give the main oxides required by calcium sulphoaluminate cement manufacture (CaO, SO₃, SiO₂, Al₂O₃)

The objective of this study was to investigate the effect of phosphogypsum addition to CKD-Fly Ash mixture, as Phosphogypsum that is rich in sulfate will enhance geopolymerization process when added in a lower dose as well as alkalis rich cement kiln dust that can positively promote geopolymerization reaction. Also elucidate the optimum dose of phosphogypsum that enhance both mechanical and microstructural properties. Also, study the geopolymer stability up on firing treatment at temperature from 300-1200°C for the optimum mixes revealed from phosphogypsum addition to fly ash-cement dust mixes and study of their microstructural impacts.

2. Experimental procedures

2.1. Materials

Materials used in this investigation are fly ash (FA) sourced from National cement company, Egypt. Phosphogypsum obtained from Abo Zabal factory for fertilizers, Egypt. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) as alkali activator purchased from SHIDO Company with a purity of 99%. Cement kiln by-pass dust CKD is a fine, highly alkaline powder that produced from cement manufacture sourced from Beni-Suef Cement Factory. The chemical composition of the starting raw materials was illustrated in Table (1). Fly ash consists of fine oxide particles and compounds such as quartz, hematite, mullite and amorphous particles, while cement dust composed mainly of calcite, sylvite and halite in a decreasing order. On the other hand, phosphogypsum consists mainly of brushite, gypsum and quartz.

Table (1): Chemical composition of starting materials. (Mass, %)

Sample name	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	SO ₃	TiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	Cl	Loss	Total	Note
Fly Ash (FA)	60.01	22.60	4.60	4.50	1.00	0.70	2.00	0.50	0.01	0.03	-	4.00	99.95	-
Phosphogypsum (PG)	32.52	0.25	0.09	27.53	0.05	0.25	0.03	38.39	0.08	0.05	0.70	0.84	99.84	-
Cement kiln dust(CKD)	8.29	2.84	2.07	51.90	0.57	2.63	3.42	2.09	0.14	0.13	6.12	19.59	99.90	Free CaO=15.5

Figure(1): Mineralogical composition of the starting raw materials. [B=Brucite($\text{CaPO}_3(\text{OH})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), G=Gypsum($\text{Ca}(\text{SO}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$), Q=Quartz(SiO_2), M=Mullite, S=Sylvite (KCl), H=Halite(NaCl), He=Hemisite(Fe_2O_3)].

2.2. Specimen preparation and test conditions

Geopolymer was made by hand mixing raw materials of each mix passing a sieve of 90 μm for 10 min and a further 5 min using mixer. Some specimens were activated using 2% NaOH, Water-binding material ratio (w/b) about 0.55 by mass. The paste mixture was cast into 25×25×25 mm cubic-shaped moulds, vibrated for compaction and sealed with a plastic cover to minimize loss of evaporable water.

All mixes were left to cure undisturbed under ambient temperature for 24 hours and subjected to curing at 60°C with 100% relative humidity. At the end of the curing regime, the specimens were subjected to the compressive strength measurements, where the resulting crushed specimens were subjected to stopping of the hydration process using stopping solution of alcohol/acetone (1:1) followed by washing with acetone as recommended by Saikia et al. (2004) for preventing further hydration and for further analysis followed by drying of the crushed specimens for 24 hrs at 80°C, then preserved in a well tight container until time of testing.

On the other hand, Firing resistant measurement was done by curing at 60°C and 100% R.H. for 28 days. The samples were calcined at different temperatures (300-1000°C) for 2 hours [24].

2.3. Methods of investigation

Chemical analysis was carried out using Axios, WD-XRF Sequential Spectrometer (Panalytical, Netherland, 2009). Compressive strength tests were carried out using five tones German Bruf pressing machine with a loading rate of 100 kg/min determined according to ASTM-C109 (2007). XRD analysis was carried out using a Philips PW 1050/70 Diffractometer. The data were identified according to the XRD software (pdf-2: database on CD-Release 2005). Microstructure of the hardened alkali activated water cooled slag was studied using SEM Inspect S (FEI Company, Netherland) equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray analyzer (EDX). Removal of free water was accomplished by using alcohol/acetone method as recommended by Saikia et al. (2004).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect phosphogypsum addition on geopolymeric behaviour

The XRD patterns of geopolymer mixes having various phosphogypsum contents and activated with 2 % NaOH cured in 100 % relative humidity, at 60°C for 90 days are shown in Fig.(2). The patterns show the increase of ettringite and gypsum with the increase of fly ash replacement by phosphogypsum (PG) which is reach in gypsum that will be transformed into ettringite when interacting with calcium aluminate phases. Calcite also exposed to an

increase in its intensity with PG increase as most of liberated free lime are exposed to carbonation, this is due to the lower pozzolanic activity of phosphogypsum in consuming free lime forming binding materials. It can be noticed also, the increase of geopolymeric glassy phase that demonstrated in the XRD pattern in the region $17-35^\circ 2\theta$. The content of the amorphous structure increases with PG up to 10%, while decrease in the higher contents as the crystalline phases prevailed.

Fig. (2): XRD pattern of 90 days alkali activated geopolymer specimens having various content of phosphogypsum, cured at 60°C and 100% relative humidity. [C: Calcite, E:Ettringite, G:Gypsum, Q: Quartz]

Morphology and microstructure of 90 days cured geopolymer specimens having various content of PG from 0 up to 30% are shown in Figure (3). Morphology of FA-CKD specimens that has no phosphogypsum content illustrate that the geopolymer configuration are tightly bound with the matrix composition, while fly ash small spheres (cenosphere) that not incorporated in the geopolymer formation cover the structure's surface, while, the structure topography seems smooth and free from pores (Fig.3a). With fly ash replacement by 10%PG (Fig.3b), the morphology seems more dense with the increase of geopolymer contribution as the excess sulfate in PG enhance fly ash dissolution and oligomer formation which in turn forms cross linked geopolymer structure. The continuous increase in fly ash replacement by PG (20%), leads matrix dilution and increase in gypsum content with its flowery microstructure that acts as a barrier against geopolymer chain formation and decrease the structure cohesion and deleterious damage in its bonds as represented in Figure (3c). Up on addition of 30%PG, ettringite content with its needle like structure increase and coagulate forming laminar sheets that prevailed in the matrix where the increase of sulfate lead to ettringite formation increase as indicated by Figure (3d). The increased ettringite content leads to the decrease in the geopolymer contribution and so lower specimen's mechanical properties.

Fig. (3): SEM micrograph of 90 days alkali activated geopolymer specimens pattern and cured at 60°C and 100% relative humidity having a) 0% PG, b)10% PG, c)20% PG and d)30% PG.

The results of compressive strength for hardened CKD-FA geopolymer, cured in 100 % R.H. at 60°C for 90 days are shown in Fig. (4). Results illustrate strength increase in all mixes along with hydration age due to propagation of pozzolanic reaction. There are two main factors that can initiate and propagate the geopolymerization reaction are alkali hydroxide and/or heating to <100°C that can form amorphous geopolymer, while >100-150°C forms zeolite of crystalline behaviour. Both activation factors are applied in the geopolymerization regime so leads to strength enhancement. Strength increase with 10%PG than the control mix which may be due to the lower dose of PG with its sulfate content can enhance geopolymer formation which is affected by both alkalis and sulfate which is present in CKD and sulfate that lies in PG, so both factors can possess an additional activation for pozzolanic or latent hydraulic fly ash materials. Both chemical and physical characteristics of the CKD and aluminosilicate source (fly ash, slag, metakaolinite etc.) play a decisive role in controlling the mechanisms of activation, the nature and amount of formed products and consequently the strength development (Konsta-Gdoutos and Shah, 2003, Wang et al., 2004, Buchwald and Schultz, 2005).

The increase of PG beyond 10 % has a negative impact on geopolymer formation as the role of sulfate is significantly clear in structure deterioration by the formation of ettringite due to sulfate attack that is very expansive since these elements could absorb moisture so that their volume of solid phase could increase to about 124 % and 227 % from the original volume [Wallah and Rangan (2006)] as represented from the following equation:

Ettringite formation is quite clear in SEM mapping of 90 days (Fig.2 c, d) so that giving an explanation about strength loss with PG increase. The XRD pattern also emphasized the ettringite formation and increase with PG increase while the geopolymer contribution decreases with PG increase as increased sulfate prevent the formation and growth of the geopolymer network as seen before in Fig.(2).

Fig. (4): Compressive strength of alkali activated geopolymer specimens having various content of phosphogypsum, cured at 60°C and 100% relative humidity.

3.2. Firing treatment on geopolymer mixes

Based on the latter section, two geopolymeric mixes have 10 and 20% PG were chosen for measuring their stability up on firing treatment from 300-1200°C; as 10%PG is the optimum mix while 20% PG exposed to a decrease in its mechanical and microstructure properties. The XRD patterns of geopolymer mixes having 10 and 20% PG, fired at 800°C for 2 hours are shown in Figure (5). The pattern indicates peaks due to quartz, mullite and hematite of the crystalline component of the fly ash can be seen in addition to a broad peak in the region 17–35° 2θ arising from the glassy phase of the fly ash. It is noticed the increase in mullite and hematite with increase in fly ash replacement by phosphogypsum. The increased mullite and hematite content with PG may be due to the destabilization of geopolymer materials that has higher PG content under high firing temperature and so the fly ash material is susceptible to disintegration into its original constituents (Mullite, Hematite and quartz).

Fig. (5): XRD pattern of alkali activated geopolymer specimens fired at 800°C having 10 and 20% phosphogypsum. [M: Mullite, H:Hematite, Q: Quartz]

Scanning electron microscope of alkali activated fly ash mix specimens that is partially replaced by phosphogypsum and fired at different firing temperatures are shown in Fig.(6). Morphology of 10 %PG specimen (Fig.6a) illustrates the presence of fly ash spheres along with spherical bright structure which is for fly ash accompanied by iron impurities that in turn lower melting point of the materials. With the increase of PG (Fig.6b), rods of ettringite appear within the structure, while fly ash spreads in the matrix. The increase of ettringite which is known by its expansive effect has a negative effect on matrix's stability and so deterioration in its microstructure as compared with 10%PG.

Fig. (6): SEM micrograph of alkali activated geopolymer specimens pattern fired at 800°C and having a) 10%PG, b) 20% PG.

The XRD patterns of geopolymer mix contain 10 % PG and fired at 800°C up to 1200°C for 2 hours are shown in Figure (7).The pattern indicates the increase in hematite, leucite and kalsilite content with temperature increase, reflecting the decomposition of matrix structure into its original constituents. Also, quartz is transformed into other polymorphs under high temperature, this polymorph increases reaching to higher intensity at 1200°C. Mullite is almost unchanged for all firing temperatures. The increase in leucite and kalsilite with firing temperature (K feldspars) in the geopolymer materials indicate decomposition of the initial aluminosilicate gel and presence of free Na, K, Si and Al. The free potassium that is exceeds than sodium in raw materials (with its low diffusion coefficient) results in an increase thermal resistance of geopolymer mix, while matrix materials remained mostly amorphous up to 1200°C [Bakharev (2006)]. In this investigation geopolymer specimens experienced recrystallization to feldspars leucite and kalsilite at 1000°C [Barbosa and Mackenzie (2003)]. There is less complete recrystallization in the silica-rich

K-Polysilicatedisiloxo samples, which retained a degree of amorphous geopolymer content on heating and had more evident melting behaviour at 1400 °C [Barbosa and Mackenzie (2003)].

Fig. (7): XRD pattern of alkali activated geopolymer specimens having 10% phosphogypsum and fired at different firing temperatures. [M:Mullite,H:Hematite,Q1:SiO₂,Q: Quartz, K: Kalsilite(KAlSiO₄), L:Lucite (KAlSi₂O₆)]

Scanning electron microscope of alkali activated fly ash mixes that is partially replaced by 10%PG and fired at different firing temperatures are shown in Fig.(8). Morphology of 800°C fired specimen (Fig.8a) illustrates the presence of fly ash spheres all over the surface and low cohesion within matrix structure. With the increase of firing temperature up to 1000°C (Fig.8b), the fly ash spheres are slightly fused in the matrix by the effect of temperature as well as the increase of amorphous leucite and kalsilite that increase structure cohesion. A significant densification was observed after firing at 1100-1200 °C [Fig. 8(c-d)] where changes that took place in the microstructure of after firing at 1100 and 1200 °C and mainly related to the increase of the amorphous K-feldspar which has low average pore size and so amorphous materials with its higher reactivity easily intact with each other.

Fig. (8): SEM micrograph of alkali activated geopolymer specimens pattern having 10% phosphogypsum and fired at a) 800°C, b)1000°C, c)1100°C, d)1200 °C

The results of compressive strength for hardened FA-CKD geopolymer fired at temperatures from 800 up to 1200°C for 2 hours with a heating rate of 5°C/min are shown in Fig.(9). The results show lower strength up to 800°C, while it increases up to 1200°C. Also, strength decrease with the increase of PG; this is attributed to the increase of sulfate

lies within PG that forms ettringite as illustrated in Figure (6b). On the other hand, the strength loss up to 800°C attributed to dehydration and dehydroxylation of geopolymer structure, after decomposition of aluminosilicate gel free sodium, potassium, silicon and aluminum produced K-feldspars, while sodium is in a trace content and has low participation in feldspar formation. The strength gain beyond 800°C is mainly due to the appearance of K-feldspars in the geopolymer materials on firing which resist thermal decomposition as seen clearly in XRD Figure (7); this can be attributed to lower diffusion K^+ in the matrix on firing [Van Vlack (1964)]. On the other hand K-gp resists temperature up to 1200, where the materials remained in the amorphous phase with reduced average pore size and significantly increase in strength due to lower diffusion coefficient of K-ions.

Fig. (9): Compressive strength of alkali activated geopolymer specimens having various content of phosphogypsum, fired at various temperatures.

Investigation of matrix development showed a decreasing average pore size and dropping porosity of the specimens after firing at 800, 1000, 1100 and 1200 °C (Fig. 8), where SEM mapping reflects the increased structure compaction and stiffness with temperature. However, significant changes of the strength at high temperatures may indicate liquid formation, which is an indication of increased thermal resistance. The materials prepared using K-containing activators lies within CKD and FA remained mostly amorphous up to 1200 °C, and had an increasing strength up to 1200 °C.

4. Conclusions

1. Addition of 10% PG positively affect the geopolymerization process and leads to increase in enhancement in mechanical and microstructure properties. While strength decreases by using higher ratio.
2. Full replacement of fly ash by phosphogypsum lower the strength approximately to 70% as related to the excess sulfate in PG forming ettringite.
3. Firing treatment from 800-1200°C shows strength lowering up to 800°C, while it increases up to 1200°C. Also, strength decrease with the increase of PG
4. Materials prepared using fly ash and cement dust reach in potassium had better thermal stability and materials remained mostly amorphous up to 1200 °C. After firing these materials had reduced average pore size and improved compressive strength.

5. References

- P. Duxson, J.L. Provis, G.C. Lukey, J.S.J. van Deventer, "The role of inorganic polymer technology in the development of 'Green concrete', *Cem. Concr. Res.* 37 (12) (2007) 1590–1597.
- J. Davidovits, "Geopolymer Chemistry and Applications", Institut Géopolymère, Saint-Quentin, France, 2008.
- J.S.J. van Deventer, J.L. Provis, P. Duxson, D.G. Brice, "Chemical research and climate change as drivers in the commercial adoption of alkali activated materials", *Waste Biomass Valoriz* 1 (1) (2010) 145–155.
- J.W. Phair, "Green chemistry for sustainable cement production and use", *Green Chem.* 8 (2006) 763–780.
- Palomo A., Grutzeck M.W. Blanco M.T., "Alkali-activated Fly Ashes – A Cement for the Future", *Cem. Con. Res.*, 29, (1999)1323-1329.
- Palomo A., Alonso S., Fernández-Jiménez A., Sobrados I., Sanz J., "Alkali activated of fly ashes. A NMR study of the reaction products", *J. Am. Ceramic. Soc.*, 87, (2004) 1141-1145.
- Fernández-Jiménez A., A. Palomo. "Composition and microstructure of alkali activated fly ash binder: Effect of the activator", *Cem. Concr. Res.*, 35, (2005)1984-1992.
- Duxon P., Fernández-Jiménez A., Provis J.L., Lukey G.C, Palomo A., Van Deventer J.S.J, , "Geopolymer technology: the current state of the art", *J. Mat. Sci.* 42(9), (2007)2917-2933.
- Dyer, T.D.; Halliday, J.E.; Dhir, R.K., "An investigation of the hydration chemistry of ternary blends containing cement kiln dust", *J. Mater. Sci.*, 34 (20), (1999)4975– 4983.
- Peethamparan S., Olek J., Lovell J.. "Influence of chemical and physical characteristics of cement kiln dusts (CKDs) on hydration behavior and potential suitability for soil stabilization". *Cem.Concr. Res.*38, (2008) 803 – 815.
- Maslehuddin M., Al-Amoudi O.S.B., Shameem M., Rehman M.K., Ibrahim M. "Usage of cement kiln dust in cement products—Research review and preliminary investigation".*Constr.Build. Mat.* 22, (2008)2369 – 2373
- Konsta-Gdoutos M.S., Shah S.P. "Hydration and properties of cements based on cement kiln dust and blast furnace slag.*Cement and Concrete Research* 33, (2003)1269-1276.
- Wang K., Shah S.P., Mishulovich A. "Effects of curing temperature and NaOH addition on hydration and strength development of clinker-free CKD-fly ash binders".*Cement and Concrete Research* 34,(2004)299-309.
- Buchwald A., Schultz M. "Alkali-activated binders by use of industrial by-products". *Cement and Concrete Research*, 35, (2005)968-973.
- Beretka, J., Cioffi, R., Marroccoli, M., Valenti, G.L."Energy-saving cements obtained from chemical gypsum and other industrial wastes". *Waste Management*, 16, (1996)231-235.
- Marroccoli, M., Nobili, M., Telesca, A., Valenti, G. L.,. "Use of wastes generated within coal-fired power stations for the synthesis of calcium sulphoaluminate cements". 7th International Conference-CONCRETE: CONSTRUCTION'S SUSTAINABLE OPTION – Role For concrete in global development, Dundee (Scotland-UK) 8-10 July 2008,299-310.
- Arjunan, K., Silsbee, M.R., Roy, D. M. "Sulfoaluminate-belite cement from low-calcium fly ash and sulphur-rich and other industrial by-products". *Cement and Concrete Research*, 29(8), (1999)1305-1311.
- Bernardo, G., Marroccoli, M., Montagnaro, F., Valenti, G.L. "Use of fluidized bed combustion wastes for the synthesis of low energy cements". 11th International Congress on the Chemistry of Cement, Durban (South Africa) 11-16 May 2003, 3, 1227-1236.
- Marroccoli, M., Montagnaro, F., Pace, M. L., Telesca, A., Valenti, G. L. "Use of fluidized bed combustion ash and other industrial wastes as raw materials for the manufacture of calcium sulphoaluminate cements". 20th International Conference on Fluidized Bed Combustion, Xi'an (China) 18-'20 May2009, 1072-1077.
- Saikia, N.; Usami, A.; Kato, S.; Kojima, T., "Hydration behavior of ecocement in presence of metakaolin", *resource progressing journal*, 51(1), (2004)35-41.
- Wenying, G.; Guolin, W.; Jianda, W.; Ziyun, W.; Suhong, Y., "Preparation and Performance of Geopolymers", *Journal of Wuhan University of Technology-Mater. Sci. Ed.*, 23(3), (2008)326-330.
- Wallah, S. E.; Rangan, B. V., "Low-calcium fly ash-based geopolymer concrete" long-term properties", *Research Report GC 2, Faculty of Engineering, Curtin University of Technology Perth, Australia, 2006.*
- Bakharev, T., "Thermal behaviour of geopolymers prepared using class F fly ash and elevated temperature curing", *Cement and Concrete Research*, 36, (2006) 1134–1147.
- Barbosa, V.F.F.; MacKenzie, K.J.D "Synthesis and thermal behaviour of potassium silicate geopolymers", *Mater. Lett.*, 57,(2003) 1477–1482.
- Van Vlack, H. "Physical Ceramics for Engineers, Addison" Wesley, London, (1964) 94–102.